

**PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT OF GRADE ONE PUPILS IN FAR FLUNG
AREAS IN RELATION TO READING PERFORMANCE:
BASIS FOR INTERVENTION**

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Parental Involvement of Grade One Pupils in Far Flung Areas in Relation to Reading Performance: Basis for Intervention

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Abstract

This study entitled Parental Involvement of Grade One Pupils in Far Flung Areas in Relation to Reading Performance: Basis for Intervention aimed to determine the relationship between the level of involvement of parents in the aspects of parenting, communicating, learning at home, and decision-making, and the reading performance of their children in terms as to being grade ready, light refresher, moderate refresher, or full refresher. Seventy-three parent-respondents answered a survey questionnaire on parental involvement, while the reading performance of grade one pupils was measured using CRLA. Findings revealed that parental involvement in parenting, communicating, learning at home, and decision-making was very high. Most of respondents' reading performance was light refresher. Significant difference was found in the parental involvement to the pupils, wherein communicating and parenting ranked the highest, indicating their importance in influencing a child's academic success. Effective communication and creating a conducive learning environment at home also played significant roles in shaping a child's reading journey. There was no significant relationship between the level of parental involvement and reading performance of the pupils, highlighting the absence of the influence of parental involvement to reading proficiency.

Keywords: *parental involvement, reading performance, grade one*

Introduction

Parental involvement refers to a parents' level of involvement in his/her child's education. From an educational standpoint, it is imperative that parents actively engage and consistently involve themselves in their children's education. It is conventional wisdom that children who have more parents who are dedicated to their children's education will ultimately be more successful (Oranga et al., 2023).

It is a partnership framework of parental involvement in school, the family, and the community that was developed by Epstein and her colleagues. It is regarded as a recent and comprehensive framework that includes various parental practices to support and enhance their children's academic performance in schools, at home, and in the community (Oranga et al., 2023) and has been adopted by numerous studies up to this point.

Learning to read is a challenge for many learners, especially those attending public schools (Mahinay, 2021). Children require a lot of help and support from their parents as well as teachers in order to attain strong reading performance and develop into effective readers. Furthermore, parents should assist their children in their studies, especially by creating a supportive environment at home, in order to inspire and encourage them to perform better in school (Pahurihay, 2021). Teachers are not the only people who have to teach reading. It is also required of the parents to support and enhance the learning that takes place in the classroom. Too many children, nevertheless, do not receive this assistance, and as a result, they are not developing to the fullest extent possible as emerging readers.

To ensure that every child can read, the Philippines government has implemented regulations and initiatives. This policy seeks to support proficient readers and increase literacy because students who struggle with reading end up with low grades, exhibit difficult behavior, become easily sidetracked and frustrated, fail to reach their full potential, and eventually stop attending school altogether. Given the importance of reading for both academic success and personal development, parents' involvement in their children's education can help them become better readers. By identifying barriers to parental participation and looking into workable ways for promoting parental involvement, educators and parents can work together to improve children's academic achievement and strong reading abilities (Epstein, 2019).

Record shows that in the District of Pontevedra II big number of learners are having problems with reading. There are those who are already promoted to higher grades but are still finding it hard to read. The researcher was motivated to find out whether involvement of parents would have a relation to their reading performance.

Thus, this study focused on parental involvement in relation to the reading performance of Grade 1 learners as the basis for intervention.

Research Questions

The purpose of the study was to determine the parental involvement of grade 1 learners in flung areas in relation to the reading performance as the basis for intervention. Specifically, this study provided answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of parental involvement on Grade 1 learners as a whole and when grouped in terms of:
 - 1.1. parenting;
 - 1.2. communicating;

- 1.3. learning at home; and
- 1.4. decision-making?
2. What is the level of learners' reading performance?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of parental involvement and reading performance of learners?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a descriptive-correlational type of research design. According to Bhat (2024), descriptive correlational research is a type of research design that tries to explain the relationship between two or more variables without making any claims about cause and effect. This study described the parental involvement of Grade 1 learners in terms of parenting, communicating, learning at home, decision-making, and the reading performance of learners. Meanwhile, the correlational part will focus on the relationship between parental involvement and the reading performance of learners.

Respondents

The subject and respondents of this study were the 73 Grade 1 parents and learners of Gomez Elementary School, Burgos Elementary School, Zamora Elementary School, and Buenavista Elementary School, in the District of Pontevedra II, Division of Negros Occidental.

Instrument

This study used two standardized questionnaires to determine parental involvement and reading performance of Grade 1 learners. First questionnaire determining the parental involvement in terms of parenting, communicating, learning at home and decision making was adapted from the study of Espinosa (2022) entitled Teaching Strategies Adopted by Parents in Facilitating Learning at Home, using the Likert Scale with the verbal descriptions of (5) Strongly Agree, (4) Agree, (3) Moderately Agree, (2) Disagree, and (1) Strongly Disagree.

Meanwhile, the second questionnaire revealing the reading performance of Grade 1 learners used the Dolch Basic Sight Words for Primers, and measured using the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) with the descriptive ratings of Grade Ready (31-40), Light Refresher (21-30), Moderate Refresher (11-20), and Full Refresher (0-10).

Procedure

The following procedures were followed by the researcher in gathering data from the respondents.

The researcher sought permission for the conduct of the study from the office of the Public Schools District Supervisor and Principals of Gomez Elementary School, Burgos Elementary School, Zamora Elementary School, and Buenavista Elementary School. Upon approval, the researcher personally administered the questionnaires through the assistance of teacher advisers of Grade 1. Questionnaires were distributed to all the advisers of Grade 1 learners and will be distributed to all parents during the conduct of Parent-Teacher Association (P. T. A.) meeting or during the distribution of Form 138. In order to gather data for the reading performance of Grade 1 learners, the researcher administered the 40-item Dolch Basic Sight Words for Primers. After the administration of the research instrument to the identified respondents, the researcher gathered the data personally, for recording, analyzing and tabulating to answer specific statement of the problem.

Data Analysis

After the data collection, the data were tallied, tabulated, and analyzed using appropriate statistical tools.

To answer statement of the problem 1 which states, what is the level of parental involvement in terms of parenting, communicating, learning at home and decision making, mean was used.

To answer statement of the problem 2 which states, what is the level Learners' Reading Performance, mean was used.

To answer statement of the problem 3 which states, is there a significant relationship between the level of parental involvement and learners' reading performance, Gamma Coefficient was used.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes and interprets the data gathered, and is arranged comprehensively to answer the statement of the problem using the appropriate statistical tool.

Level of Parental Involvement on Grade 1 Learners When Taken as a Whole and When Grouped in Terms of Parenting, Communicating, Learning at Home, and Decision Making

The table below presents the level of parental involvement in Grade 1 learners.

The data shows that under parental involvement, parenting has a mean score of 4.32, which was interpreted as very high.

Communicating has a 4.33 mean score and was also interpreted as very high. As for learning at home, the mean score of 4.28 was also a very high level. Decision-making has a mean score of 4.26 with a very high level. As a whole, parental involvement garners a mean score of 4.30 and is interpreted as a very high level.

Table 1. *Level of Parental Involvement on Grade 1 Learners Taken as a Whole and Grouped in Terms of Parenting, Communicating, Learning at Home, and Decision Making*

<i>Parental Involvement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Parenting	4.32	Very High
Communicating	4.33	Very High
Learning at home	4.28	Very High
Decision-making	4.26	Very High
As a whole	4.30	Very High

This implies that the parental involvement of parents to the learners was good and commendable, and they must have made some extraordinary efforts to help their children succeed in their reading performance. This is consistent with research findings by Tang et al. (2018), which found that parenting practices had a big impact on kids' motivation for school. Furthermore, there was a correlation between increased intrinsic motivation and recognized regulation and the authoritative parenting approaches of mothers. Furthermore, there was a negative correlation found between moms' authoritarian parenting approaches and both external and introjected control. Finally, there was a positive correlation found between the permissive parenting styles of fathers and mothers and external regulation.

Furthermore, Llego (2021) emphasized that parental involvement plays a crucial role in ensuring children's educational achievement. Children are more likely to perform well in school and develop socially and emotionally when their parents are involved in their education.

Additionally, a dominant parenting style can benefit students' reading development. An assertive parenting style has been associated with certain good traits in young children and teenagers, claims Pace (2022). Furthermore, authoritative parents never stop praising their kids, highlighting their accomplishments, and supporting them as they work on their shortcomings. They also never stop enjoying every little triumph. Since their parents value and acknowledge their accomplishments, children are encouraged to put in a lot of effort and work hard.

In communicating, a good basis of communication serves as the cornerstone of a healthy relationship. The capacity to communicate effectively is arguably the most vital life skill. This is especially important when it comes to parent-child relationships. Building empathy and fostering trust are two benefits of good parent-child communication. Speaking is not the only thing that goes into engaging. It all comes down to feeling and hearing what your youngster has to say (Podium School, 2021). Effective communication also helps the youngster grow into a happy, responsible adult. Better communication skills are also developed in the child, which will be helpful in the future. Similarly, students whose parents make positive school-related conversations, engage in positive after-school activities, and assist their kids in making college support plans are more likely to: regularly attend school, consistently turn in their homework, achieve higher grades and test scores, adjust well in the classroom, and improve their social skills (Waterford, 2022). As a result, a vital component of a kid's education is communication with both the child and other stakeholders. A child's intellectual growth can be maximized with appropriate communication.

Research on students' learning at home has revealed that parenting and learning at home are both significant factors that improve children's abilities and academic performance. A study conducted by Sabrina and Adam (2022) discovered that parental involvement in child-centered numeracy activities can improve children's mathematical skills, particularly for those in preschools. In a study investigating the influence of parental involvement on early childhood education, Yiran et al. (2021) found that parents' views towards their children's education as well as their involvement in educational activities have a positive effect on the math performance of their children.

On decision-making, students' abilities to come up with sound decisions indicate that parental involvement in a child's education may enhance the child's social and emotional development as well as their feeling of self-worth and academic achievement. Investing in their children's education allows parents to better support their academic success, help them develop important life skills, and make them feel good about themselves (Jesionkowska et al., 2020). According to the data, parental involvement significantly predicts a student's achievement in the classroom (Papadakis et al., 2020). If parents actively participate in their children's education, they can help them succeed in school and reach their full potential.

Level of Reading Performance of Learners

The table presented below shows the level of reading performance of Grade 1 learners.

The table shows that out of a total sample size of 73 learners, 7 of them are categorized as grade ready, 66 are light refresher, and none fall into the moderate refresher and full refresher categories. Entirely, the reading performance of the learners gains a mean of 13.34, indicating a light refresher level of reading intervention. The findings demonstrate that Grade 1 learners acquire a firm grasp of reading concepts and skills, and need ample practice for mastery and accuracy.

Table 2. *Level of Reading Performance of Learners*

<i>Level of Learners' Reading Performance</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Grade Ready	7		
Light Refresher	66		
Moderate Refresher	0	13.34	Light Refresher
Full Refresher	0		
Total	73		

The result is in line with the study of Ditona & Rico (2021) that in reading, the reader and the text engage in a variety of interaction processes where the reader applies their knowledge to develop, generate, and construct meaning. There are three key themes in the realm of reading identified by the National Reading Panel; first, learning new words and receiving instruction are important aspects of reading, which requires sophisticated cognitive processes; second, understanding a book requires deliberate effort and frequently draws on past knowledge; and lastly, educators have to help students apply the techniques that lead to successful reading.

According to DepEd (2019), the average reading literacy performance in the Philippines is one level below the minimal competence level, falling inside the proficiency level. This shows that, on the whole, Filipino students can comprehend sentences or brief sections in their literal sense, identify the primary idea, and draw a single conclusion from several related bits of information. Thus, all schools are required to create a School-Based Reading Program, which entails conducting a reading ability assessment of the students, identifying the students who require more reading instruction, and implementing the necessary strategies to enhance reading comprehension.

Relationship Between the Level of Parental Involvement and Level of Reading Performance of Learners

The table below presents the relationship between the level of parental involvement and the level of reading performance of learners.

Table 3. *Relationship Between the Level of Parental Involvement and Level of Reading Performance of Learners*

<i>Level of Parental Involvement</i>	<i>Level of Learners' Reading Performance</i>				<i>Total</i>
	<i>Grade Ready</i>	<i>Light Refresher</i>	<i>Moderate Refresher</i>	<i>Full Refresher</i>	
Very High	6	66	0	0	72
High	1	0	0	0	1
Moderate	0	0	0	0	0
Low	0	0	0	0	0
Very Low	0	0	0	0	0
Total	7	66	0	0	73

Computed value (G): -1.00

p-value: 0.308

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table displays the relationship between parental involvement levels and reading performance levels among 73 respondents. It shows that 72 learners with very high level of parental involvement wherein 6 of them were grade ready and 66 were light refresher, whereas only one learner with a high level of parental involvement and a grade ready reading performance.

The relationship between the level of parental involvement and the level of reading performance of learners obtains a computed value of -1.00, and a p-value of 0.308 which is lower than the 0.05 level of significance, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This implies that there is no significant relationship between the level of parental involvement and the level of reading performance of learners.

The aforementioned results contradict the findings of Alfano et al. (2022), who demonstrated that one of the most significant determinants of language and emerging literacy is unquestionably parental involvement in their child's reading. Furthermore, Boonk et al. (2018) found that parental involvement in reading at home is a potential way to support early elementary school reading acquisition and is favorably correlated with later accomplishment, especially in spoken language and literacy. Therefore, parents ought to be actively involved in their children's reading activities. They ought to understand how important it is for them to be involved in their kids' reading development. Parents who read aloud to their kids set them up for success in school when it comes to literacy and reading. Children's involvement with reading in general (Reese et al. 2022) and the parent-child connection (Canfeld et al., 2020) may both benefit from maintaining these significant, high-quality reading encounters with parents.

Reading proficiency is positively impacted by parents teaching their children to read at home. It suggests that when parents support, stay with, and give their children the reading tools they need, their children become motivated and self-assured in their ability to read both at home and at school. Activities for assisting the child with homework or other lesson-related duties are included in the category of "learning at home." In addition to helping with schoolwork and helping their kids acquire the essential skills, parents can have conversations with their kids about school at home (Caliskana, 2022).

Parents and teachers share responsibility for their children's reading and comprehension abilities. By spending time at home teaching their children to read and understand what they are reading, parents can significantly increase their children's reading proficiency.

Parents' involvement in reading at home was found to be a promising kind of involvement throughout the early primary school years and reading acquisition. Boonk et al. (2018) found that this involvement was positively connected with later accomplishment, notably in oral and language and literacy.

Parenting greatly affects the learners' reading performance. This implies that a child's ability to read is greatly influenced by their parents' parenting. It is fundamental for their children to advance in all areas of their life, not only in reading. Parents should help their children in their studies, especially by creating a supportive environment at home, to inspire and encourage them to perform better in school. Bendanillo, 2021 cited that given the importance of support from home in helping children develop essential language and early literacy experiences, parental involvement has been widely supported to be an effective strategy in increasing academic growth.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

Parental involvement in parenting, communicating, learning at home, and decision-making have all been rated as very high by the respondents.

Learners' reading performance is light refresher, indicating that they exhibit firm understanding and skills in reading, yet need little improvement for accuracy. The absence of any respondents categorized as full refreshers implies that there may be room for improvement and development in reading proficiency.

Parental involvement of the learners does not influence their reading performance. Additionally, parental involvement does not affect the improvement nor the decline of the learners' reading performance.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are stated for the favorable action of the concerned:

Schools Administrators may continue to encourage and facilitate high levels of parental involvement to enhance the academic outcomes of students, and enhance curriculum for primary learners optimizing parental support in reading proficiency of learners.

School Heads can implement regular assessments and tracking progress could help in measuring the effectiveness of any interventions and inform future strategies.

Teachers may develop targeted refresher programs tailored to address the specific needs of the light refresher group, to further enhance their reading skills.

Parents can look for a school that offers targeted programs or resources to improve reading skills with specialized interventions or support systems in place to help students enhance their reading proficiency, thereby enabling them to reach their full potential academically.

Parents may prioritize their involvement in decision-making processes regarding their child's education, as well as focus on effective communication and fostering a positive learning environment at home, they can be aware of their influence and take proactive steps to support and enhance their child's learning outcomes through consistent involvement and encouragement.

Future researchers may conduct a more comprehensive study related to this with a larger population to capture a much wider perspective.

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